

INFLUENCE OF ROAD WIDTH ON ROAD TRAFFIC SAFETY

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Annotation: The article analyzes opinions and comments on the concept of impact on traffic safety, the impact of road width on road safety, legal norms regulating road safety, and the experience of some foreign countries is promoted. Proposals have been put forward to improve the efficiency of road safety.

Key words: road width, traffic flow density, road capacity, dynamic gauge, road category

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important tasks performed in the city's road network is to organize safe movement of traffic, pedestrians and cyclists along the network, to eliminate traffic congestion, to check the ability to pass the road, to divide the street. ensuring optimal speed and reducing traffic accidents. The use of technical means and methods of traffic organization in the implementation of the listed

measures and in increasing the operational performance of city roads and streets is not only for the correct organization of traffic, but also for the safety of traffic and effectively affects the calculation of road capacity. Also, the above-mentioned activities are cheap compared to street reconstruction, and should be considered as the first step to improve the traffic conditions of city roads and streets before capital road works [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organization of traffic means the maximum use of the geometric dimensions of the road to ensure a safe movement order and high throughput in its various sections.

It is necessary to distinguish between the work of motor transport, the work of the driver, the organization of the movement of vehicles and pedestrians on the road. The first two issues are mainly dealt with by automobile companies, and with the latter by road companies, traffic safety bodies and authorities.

Traffic on highways is irregular. Each driver chooses a convenient mode of movement and does not consider the effect of the chosen mode of movement on other traffic participants. Also, the width of the city streets and highways, the quality of the dynamic dimensions of different models of cars inevitably affect the traffic order. The interaction of cars in traffic increases as much as the volume of traffic increases.

It is understood that the main goal of road width organization is to safely pass various vehicles at high speed through different sections of the road in any weather conditions of the year [3].

- The main tasks of the road inspector in the organization of the movement are as follows:
- determining and ensuring the order of movement of vehicles;
- to ensure high-efficiency operation of cars in any weather conditions and create the best road conditions;

- ensuring traffic safety on any part of the road and in different weather conditions;
- not to pollute the ecological state of the environment;
- ensuring that vehicles and road structures do not fail quickly.
- reducing traffic jams

The following activities are planned for the division of traffic safety by directions [4]:

1. With the help of a separating strip, the traffic section of the road in separate directions is placed on a single road bed.
2. Placing the traffic section on a separate road.
3. Installation of safety islands separating the directions in curves with a small radius where visibility is not provided.
4. Organization of one-way traffic on parallel streets in residential areas.
5. Placement of roads intersecting at intersections at different levels.

The width of the road has an effect on the maximum and theoretical carrying capacity of the road.

The narrowness of the road leads to a decrease in the number of light vehicles that can be passed through favorable road conditions in an idealized manner, that is, to a decrease in the maximum carrying capacity of the road [5].

An increase in the speed of cars, the inadequacy of the road category for traffic on the traffic section of the inner streets of the city, causing some inconveniences between cars or pedestrians and cars during traffic, or when a road traffic accident occurs. can lead to In addition, in favorable weather conditions, the maximum number of cars that can be passed through a specific road section according to a certain traffic order (the theoretical capacity of the road) will decrease.

The components of the dynamic dimensions of cars are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Dynamic gauge of cars

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the large-scale reforms carried out on the basis of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the period of 2022-2026 and the national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030, of course, in strengthening road safety, in addition, it is effective in improving the norms of administrative and legal regulation.

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